

TEACHING ENGLISH IN INCLUSIVE EDUCATION BASED ON SMART TECHNOLOGY

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Abstract: *This article discusses the introduction Inclusive education, the issue of teaching English to students in higher education institutions based on STEAM technology. In addition, the concept and structure of Inclusive education is analyzed.*

Key words: *Inclusive education, structure, STEAM technology, reflexive, creative, motivational.*

Annotatsiya: *Ushbu maqolada inklyuziv ta'limning joriy etilishi, STEAM texnologiyasi asosida oliy ta'lim muassasalarida talabalarga ingliz tilini o'qitish masalasi muhokama qilinadi. Bundan tashqari, inklyuziv ta'lim tushunchasi va tuzilishi ham tahlilga tortilgan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *inkluziv ta'lim, struktura, STEAM texnologiyasi, refleksiya, kreativ, motivatsion.*

INTRODUCTION

Inclusive education considers the educational process much more broadly than integration, allows to change and adapt educational methods and tools for all categories of the population, taking into account the individual characteristics of each person.

Therefore, the purpose of inclusive education is to ensure that students with special needs receive adequate education in higher education institutions, and to create the necessary conditions for every child in educational institutions.

With the advent of inclusive education for everyone (primary, secondary, higher and additional), many teachers faced problems related to ignorance of the specifics of

working with people with limited health desires (HIA) and disabilities, as well as psychological disorders and symptoms, manifestations with many years of opinion about the insolvency of this category of the population. Therefore, many consider inclusive competence to be a priority even before the start of the practical professional activities of specialists, i.e. in the process of obtaining education.

LITERATURE REVIEW AND METHODS

Different definitions of this concept can be found in pedagogical literature (See Table 1):

Table 1.

The scientists' views on the concept of inclusive competence

№	Name	The author's views
1.	O. A. Kozireva	a set of skills and abilities of a teacher in creating conditions for the implementation of educational activities of people with disabilities and disabilities, the ability of a teacher to adapt and transform teaching methods and means to meet the educational needs of all categories of the population [9]
2.	I. N. Khafizullina	a component that constitutes professional competence, which is mandatory for a qualified teacher [11]
3.	O. V. Klezovich	an integrative professional characteristic of the personality and activity of a teacher in an inclusive practice, which is characterized by a set of interrelated value-semantic orientations, inclusive knowledge and skills, methods and experience of activity, professional and personal qualities of a teacher, as well as the ability to introspect one's own activities, allowing to effectively carry out the learning process in an inclusive environment, taking into account the various educational needs of students for the purpose of personal development and self-development of each of them
4.	V.V. Khitryuk	the inclusive readiness of a teacher is considered as a systemic characteristic of the personality of the subject of professional and pedagogical activity, including willingness to act in a certain way [12]

In their work, researchers believe that there are a number of structures of inclusive competence, and we consider them in the table below (See Table 2):

Table 2.

The structure of inclusive competence

In inclusive classes, modern technologies have a wide range of opportunities for organizing general activities of students. In particular, STEAM technologies are effective in differential and individual work with students due to their reflexivity, creativity, and motivational orientation.

The STEAM program is distinguished by active communication and teamwork. During the dialogue period, a free environment is created to express one's opinion and conduct a debate. They learn to speak and make presentations. If children always participate with the teacher and classmates, they will remember the activity well.

It is shown that the use of “creative spaces” for the implementation of students' project activities, the inclusion of the category “language” in its content allows students to form the necessary skills and competencies, that is, the proposed model can be considered as a benefit tool for high-quality preparation of students for professional activities in modern conditions (See Picture 1):

Picture 1. Benefits of STEAM technology in inclusive education

CONCLUSION

It can be concluded that STEAM education allows training of highly qualified specialists who will make a great contribution to the development of society and the state. The purpose of this approach is to systematically involve schools, higher education, the public, and promote scientific literacy and competitiveness in ensuring the sustainable development of the world's development and economy through education.

It is known from the information presented above that the diversity of the components of the inclusive competence shows the uncertainty of defining the content of this concept, as well as the importance of taking into account the important features.

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